

Representation of structural knowledge in stylistic techniques

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Abstract: This article analyses the use of the poetic details as a deep meaning, Firstly, an analogy is drawn between an imaginary and a real sandcastle, and secondly, a contrast is created between the figurative and subject-logical knowledge of the “sandcastle” lexeme, between the real and illusory world of the main character. Secondly, contrast enhances the stylistic and conceptual significance of the phenomena presented in contrast and thus emphasizes and highlights the information contained in the text about the illusory world of the main character. Just as it is impossible to build a sand castle, all the dreams and hopes of the heroine seem impossible.

Keywords: cognitive structure, poetic detail, rhetorical questions, interaction, significant quantity, a literary text, figurative, metaphorical

Introduction: As already noted, a new approach to the concept of a stylistic device involves considering it as a cognitive structure that conveys certain structures of knowledge about the world. In this regard, of particular interest are conceptual metaphors that form new individual author's knowledge on the basis of known collective knowledge about the world, symbols expressing the conceptual information of the entire work, antonomasia and allusion, acting as representatives of encyclopedic information of a literary, mythological, religious nature. To illustrate, for example, the stylistic device of a symbol, let us turn to A. Murdoch's novel Sandcastle. The very title of the novel, which is symbolic, expresses the main idea of the author - to show the illusory world of the characters.

The problem of the symbol as a stylistic device is quite well studied, since many studies have been devoted to it (Ch. Pierce, A.F. Losev, A.A. Potebnya, S.S. Averintsev, V.V. Vinogradov, N.D. Arutyunova, V. M. Markov, V. V. Kolesov, V. N. Toporov, P. A. Florensky, M. E. Eliada, E. V. Shelestyuk, N. M. Dzhusupov). According to the concept of N.M. Dzhusupov's symbol is a cognitively significant unit that conveys certain structures of knowledge and is determined by such factors as: 1) recurrence factor; 2) accent factor; 3) the factor of representation of knowledge structures; 4) the conceptualization factor. In the analyzed novel, the recurrence factor is represented by a three-fold repetition of the lexeme "sandcastle". As for the factor of representation of knowledge structures, it is very important to note that with each use of this symbol, new conceptual meanings arise, which, as a rule, are of an implicit nature. The symbolic significance of this image is manifested primarily in the fact that this symbol is used in the title of the work. As you know, the title is the most important, conceptually significant component of a literary text. The problem of the title has always attracted the attention of researchers and has been studied in various aspects of its consideration: structural-semantic, stylistic, pragmatic Halperin, Morokhovsky ... [p. 362 Dzhusupov] Of greatest interest is the cognitive-stylistic aspect of the title, which is the subject of research by N. Dzhusupov and N. Normurodova. From the standpoint of the cognitive theory of language, the title is considered as a cognitive structure in a compressed, compressive form representing the knowledge embedded in the content of the entire text.

In the analyzed work, the title correlates, first of all, with a poetic detail containing information about the childhood of the main character Rhine, passing on the Mediterranean coast and vain *tideless sea. I can recall, as a child, seeing pictures in English children's books of boys and girls playing on the sand and making sandcastles - and I tried to play on my sand. But a Mediterranean beach is not a place for playing on. It is dirty and very dry. The tides never wash the sand or make it firm. When I tried to make a sandcastle, the sand would just run away between my fingers. It was too dry to hold together. And even if I poured sea water over it, the sun would dry it up at once* [p.106] .

The use of this poetic detail has a deep meaning, because firstly, an analogy is drawn between an imaginary and a real sandcastle, and secondly, a contrast is created between the figurative and subject-logical knowledge of the “sandcastle” lexeme, between the real and illusory world of the

main character. Contrast, as you know, enhances the stylistic and conceptual significance of the phenomena presented in contrast and thus emphasizes and highlights the information contained in the text about the illusory world of the main character. Just as it is impossible to build a sand castle, all the dreams and hopes of the heroine seem impossible. Based on the content of the text, Rain Mor dream of true love, family happiness and a beautiful life, but life circumstances are strong and destroy their plans. Let's consider a fragment of the text, which contains the arguments of the characters about their future life together. Rain expresses his doubts about the possibility of being happy together. Her feelings are expressed through rhetorical questions (*“but then what would happen?”*, *“But what about yours?”*, *“Would it in the end satisfy you just to be with me?”*, *“ Would you be able to write and to go on writing?”*, *“ If you had really wanted to write as much as I want to paint you would have written by now, you would have found the time somehow, nothing would have stopped you”*), which convey the inner psychological state of the heroine, her awareness of the unrealizability of hope for happiness. More's speech expresses his love for a girl (*“You made me exist for the first time”*, *“ I began to be when I loved you, I saw the world for the first time, the beautiful world full of things and animals that I'd never seen before ”*), but also some doubts conveyed by the use of the subjunctive mood (*“ I could make my life with you”*), риторических вопросов (*“What sort of life do you think I have now....?”* , *“What do you think will hop-pen to me if you leave me now?”*). Thus, these statements also emphasize the idea of the impossibility, the impracticability of the dream of happiness.

An important component of the conceptual picture of the world of this work is also the names of the characters *Rain* and *More*, which also correlate with the title of the work and receive symbolic significance. **“Rain”** is associated primarily with negative emotions, as evidenced by its associative connections: **“Rain”** - a steady falling of water from the sky in significant quantity (cloudburst, deluge, downpour, rainfall, rainstorm, storm, wet, Words related to rain: precipitation (precipitation), shower, thundershower, thunderstorm, weather, barrage barrage, bombardment, broadside, cannonade, fusillade - shooting, salvo-volley, volleyflood salvo flood, gush gush, rush rush, spate ass, back, torrent - flow, eruption - eruption, outbreak - outbreak, outburst - outbreak

As for the anthroponym *More*, it is allusive, associated with the famous work of Thomas More "Utopia (Utopia)". Thus, a direct parallel can be drawn between the title of the work and the name of the character. utopia means “Utopia – an imagined place or state of things in which everything is perfect. The word was first used as the name of an imaginary island, governed on a perfect political and social system, in the book Utopia (1516) by Sir Thomas More. The name in modern Latin literally ‘no-place’, from Greek ‘ou’ not + topos ‘place’” (Merriam-Webster Thesaurus)

It is interesting to note that this symbol is based on the interaction of two types of knowledge structures: collective, fixed in human experience and reflected in lexicographic sources: *“Sandcastle - 1. a small castle like structure made of wet sand by children at a beach”* and individual author's knowledge that interprets this concept in their figurative, metaphorical meaning. Based on the analysis of text associations, certain conclusions can be drawn regarding the “castle” built in the mind of the heroine. But like a sand castle, all hopes collapsed, dreams turned out to be unrealizable, and love could not stand the circumstances of real life. It is no coincidence that the text of the work uses many verbs that convey the idea of destruction, collapse, annihilation, death: *“break”, “wreck”, “die”, “having deprived”, “kill”*. *“I had just not realized that I was wrecking your whole life. I see it all quite differently now. I see your children, I see your ambitions. You love me, yes. But you wouldn't really forgive me for having deprived you of so much. And I wouldn't forgive myself for doing so’. She spoke in amonotonous slightly whining voice, and her tears were very slow but ceaseless.*

“What I doing in your life. I've often wondered this you know, only I never told my doubts. You are a growing tree. I am only a bird. You cannot break your roots and fly away with me. Where could we go where you wouldn't always be wanting the deep things that belong to you, your children, and this work which you know is your work? I know how I would feel if were prevented from painting. I should die if I were preventing from painting. I should die.

You would be happy with me for “short while”, said Rain, but then what would happen? It’s all dry sand running through the fingers. I am wander about the world and where ever I go I can print If we were together my work could continue.

Individual-author's knowledge containing information about aesthetic attitudes, its value orientations and author's modality. Individual author's knowledge is a reflection of the author's artistic picture of the world. Associative links of this lexeme testify to instability, shakiness. The use of this poetic detail in its direct denotative meanings emphasizes the conceptual meaning of the symbol, introducing into it the idea of ephemerality, transience, fragility, illusory nature of the fantasies built by the heroine.

Of great interest in terms of representing the structures of encyclopedic knowledge of a literary, mythological, historical, religious nature are such stylistic devices as allusion and antonomasia. As you know, antonomasia is represented by two types: 1) a proper name in the meaning of a common noun, represented by a well-known name and used to denote a specific concept; 2) a common noun in the meaning of one's own, used as a designation for the name of a person [Galperin]. The first type of antonomasia is allusive, because contains an indication of a well-known person. It is this type of antonomasia that is the representative of encyclopedic knowledge.

In this reason we should know that theonymy a set of theonymic names; a branch of lexicology that studies the lexical meanings of the specific and general names of gods and spirits in relation to their systematic organization, operation, development, etymology, as well as other categories of specific and general lexicons.

Let us turn to the analysis of the language material in O’Henry’s story “*A Madison Square Arabian Nights*”. This story is interesting in that it is built entirely on allusive references, starting with the title of the work (“*A Madison Square Arabian Nights*”) and repeated use of allusions (“*Caliph*”, “*Bagdad*”, “*Bagdad-on-the Subway*”, “*Haroun al Raschids*”, “*Scheherezade*”, “*genie*”) in the text of the story. All allusive expressions used in the story contain structures of literary knowledge about the famous monument of medieval Arabic and Persian literature, the collection of fairy tales and short stories “*A Thousand and One Nights*”. The structures of knowledge about Scheherazade, Aladdin, genies, caliph Al-Rashid, the ruler of Baghdad and patron of the arts embedded in this work help the reader to understand the conceptual meaning of the work. It is important to note that the allusions used in the text, representing the structures of knowledge of a literary nature, also perform a number of cognitive and stylistic functions. These are the functions of “*drawing the reader’s attention*” (*attractive function*), the function of creating interest, the expressive amplifying function (*accentuating*), as well as the function of creating an artistic image of a character (*designing function*).

Conclusion: Analyzing these allusions and their functions, one can draw certain conclusions regarding the image of the artist. This person, despite a beggarly, miserable existence (“*They put me out of business*”, “*I began to rest my weary head upon the breast of Old Boose*”, “*And pretty soon I was in the free bed like*”) is characterized as a person with a rich imagination, excellent education, creative creative thinking. This conclusion leads to the decoding of implicit information expressed by the content of the entire text as a whole and by allusions in particular.

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